

**A STUDY ON THE EFFICACY OF MGNREGA IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC
DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ARALAM
GRAMA PANCHAYATH, KERALA, INDIA**

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Abstract

There have been discussions about women's status in family and society over the years. Women are considered as the weaker sections in our society and they have poor socio-economic conditions as compared to men. The Absence of employment is one of the major issues among women which create effects on their socio-economic status in the society as compared to men.

Here the Researchers tried to study about the efficacy of MGNREGA in the socio-economic development of women. The Researchers took 80 samples from Aralam Grama Panchayath in Kannur district. The Objective of the study was to know the efficacy of MGNREGA in the formation of socio-economic development of women. The Methodology used was Mixed Method Research. Empirical tool was adopted first to collect the data from the field and hence in order to increase the reliability of knowledge the researchers did case Studies. It was convergent findings that substantiated the empirical data in its richness. The Study brought out some unique findings which are very relevant and inevitable in the overall development of MGNREGA.

Key words: MGNREGA, Efficacy, Socio-Economic Development, Empowerment and Women

INTRODUCTION

Mahatma Gandhi had said, “India lives in its villages. If village perishes India will perish too. India will be no more India. Her own mission in the world will get lost”. He could not be more accurate, for nearly three-fourth of the nation’s 125 crore population lives in rural areas and about two-third of the work-force in the country depend on agriculture for their livelihood. Because though contribution of agriculture to national GDP has come down from over 50 per cent in the first decade after independence to less than 15 per cent in the recent years, rural India and its development forms the priority in formulation of government policies and programmes. The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, NREGA, also known as National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme, NREGS is an Indian job guarantee scheme, enacted by legislation on August 25, 2005.

The NREGA provides a legal guarantee for one hundred days of employment in every financial year to adult. There was no guarantee that employment would be available to rural households on demand. By taking into account, the experience gained under the past wage employment generating scheme. It was decided to launch a programme to secure wage employment for the households in the rural areas. For improving the living standards of low-income population residing in rural areas and making the process of their development self-sustaining, the Indian citizens are guaranteed employment by the government. As demand driven programme MGNREGA was passed by the government of India on August 5, 2005. The basic objective of the Act is to enhance livelihood security in rural areas by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work. MGNREGA is a powerful instrument for ensuring inclusive growth in rural India through its impact on social protection, livelihood security and democratic empowerment. It attempts to bridge the gap between the rich and poor in the country.

MGNREGA stipulates that works must be targeted towards a set of specific activities which provides an opportunity to build rural infrastructure through water conservation and harvesting, renovation of water bodies, land development, soil erosion, soil control, rural connectivity and so on. MGNREGA came into force on 7th September 2005 and its implementation was in phased manner. The Act was notified in 200 districts in the first phase with effect from February 2, 2006 and then extended to an additional 130 districts in the financial year 2007-08 (113 districts were notified with effect from April 1, 2007 and 17

districts were notified with effect from May 15, 2007). The remaining districts have been notified under MGNREGA with effect from April 1, 2008. Thus, the MGNREGA covers the entire country with the exception of districts that have a hundred per cent urban population. The National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (NREGA) has renamed as Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGA) on October 2, 2009 as a humble tribute to the father of nation.

Almost a decade of application, MGNREGS in India has been positive in ensuring livelihood for the deprived people in rural areas. During the year 2013-14, 3.8 crores household were given employment and a total of 135 crores person-days of employment have been produced. Out the 135 crore, 73.33 crore were for women, 21.09 crore for STs, and 31.53 crore for SCs. A total of 111 Lakhs job were taken up of which 11.17 lakhs have been completed so far and remaining jobs are in progress. In the 1st phase of execution of NREGA 2006-07, 2.10 crore public got 100 days employment during the period. This comprises water harvesting and conservation 3.40 lakh, face-lift of traditional water bodies 96 thousand, provision of irrigation amenity 1.58 lakh, and small irrigation works 53 thousand, land growth 1.17 lakh, rural connectivity 2.03 lakh. Drought proofing nearly 1.13 lakh, flood control and safety 20 thousand.

Eempowerment (or female empowerment) is the process of empowering women. It may be defined in several ways, including accepting women's viewpoints or making an effort to seek them, raising the status of women through education, awareness, literacy, and training. Women's empowerment equips and allows women to make life-determining decisions through the different problems in society. They may have the opportunity to redefine gender roles or other such roles, which in turn may allow them more freedom to pursue desired goals. Women's empowerment has become a significant topic of discussion in development and economics. Economic empowerment allows women to control and benefit from resources, assets, and income. It also aids the ability to manage risk and improve women's well-being. It can result in approaches to support trivialized genders in a particular political or social context.

While often interchangeably used, the more comprehensive concept of gender empowerment, concerns people of any gender, stressing the distinction between biological and gender as a role. Nations, businesses, communities and groups may benefit from the implementation of programs and policies that adopt the notion of female empowerment.

Empowerment of women enhances the quality and the quantity of human resources available for development. Empowerment is one of the main procedural concerns when addressing human rights and development. Women Empowerment is the process that creates power in women to live a happy and respectable life in a society. Women are empowered when they are able to access opportunities in a variety of fields such as in education, profession, lifestyle, etc., without any limitations and restrictions. It includes raising their status through education, awareness, literacy and training. It also includes the authority to take decisions. When a woman makes a crucial decision, she feels empowered.

Women's empowerment is the most crucial point for the overall development of a country. Suppose, in a family, there is one earning person, while in another family, both men and women are earning, then who will have a better lifestyle. The answer is simple, the family where both men and women are earning money. Thus, the country where men and women work together develops at a faster rate.

The Sati Pratha in the ancient times to the girl child abortion, in the present scenario, women continue facing such violence. Not only this, heinous crimes against women such as rape, acid attack, dowry system, honor killing, domestic violence, and so on are still happening in India. Out of the total population, 50% of the population should consist of women. However, due to female feticide practices, girl child numbers are decreasing sharply in India. It has also impacted the sex ratio in India. The literacy rate in girls is very low. Most of the girls are not even provided with primary education. Moreover, they are married early and made to raise children and shoulder only household work. They are not allowed to go out and are dominated by their husbands. Women are taken for granted by men as they are considered their property. Even at the workplace, women are discriminated against. They are paid less for the same work as compared to their male counterparts. Women can be empowered in various ways. It can be done through government schemes as well as on an individual basis. At the individual level, we should start respecting women and start giving them opportunities equal to men. We should promote and encourage them to take up jobs, higher education, business activities and so on.

The Government has come up with various schemes such as Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Yojana, Mahila-E-Haat, Mahila Shakti Kendra, Working Women Hostel, Sukanya Samridhi Yojana, and so on to empower women. Apart from these schemes, we as individuals can also empower women by abolishing social evils like the dowry system, child marriage. These small steps will change the situation of women in society and make them feel empowered.

The Empowerment of rural women is crucial for the development of the rural Bharat. Women have to empower themselves from below in order to make the government to empower them from above. In the words “empowering women is a precondition for creating a good nation, when women are empowered, society with stability is assured”. The MGNREGA has positive impact on empowerment and employment pattern of women in recent years. It aims at enhancing livelihood security by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every rural household especially for women. Women participation has increased significantly and perceived it giving them a sense of independence and security. Country should be alerted with proper education and also they should be entrusted with all sorts of works as per their physical capability”. Women are needed as part of the world. They play important role in the growth of the society as well as the country. The definition of women is actually different for different persons but there is an essential base that cannot change regardless of nationality, caste, color, profession, when women support to empower themselves the whole society benefits and families are healthier. Therefore, it is very important to empower women. Empowerment of women refers to the influence of decision making of their own.

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is a landmark legislation passed by the parliament of India after a successful struggle for employment guarantee legislation. MGNREGA as a flagship programme of Government of India was notified on September 7, 2005 in 200 rural districts in its first phase of implementation which took an effect from February 2, 2006. In 2007–08, it was extended to an additional 130 rural districts. The remaining districts were notified under MGNREGA with effect from April 1, 2008. Since then MGNREGA has covered the entire country with the exception of districts that have a hundred percent urban population. The main objective of the Act is to enhance livelihood security of the rural household by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work. It was essentially a programme to provide basic income and employment opportunities to poor households in rural areas where opportunities of work did not exist or was very limited. The programme is different from earlier wage employment programmes in terms of its right based and demand driven approach to public work. This Act is the largest ever public programme that goes beyond poverty alleviation and recognizes employment as a legal right.

MGNREGS is a demand driven public programme in the history initiated for the transformation of rural households. It creates the right to work and goes beyond poverty alleviation and recognizes employment as a legal right. The effective implementation of the scheme would take the economy for sustainable growth; helps to reduce poverty by developing social infrastructure and it provide long term strong foundation for agriculture. Any how the success of the programme lies in active participation and the work involvement of the workers. Therefore to assess the awareness regarding the provisions of the scheme, the overall performance of the scheme and to assess the impact of the scheme on various development indicators such as income and employment generation, livelihood security, creation and durability of productive assets, distress migration, household savings and indebtedness, land and water conservation, agriculture productivity and wages, women empowerment, household empowerment and the overall village level impact. There are some of the major issues which require a study and an analysis. Hence it is necessary to study the awareness, performance and the impact of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The MGNREGA has been implementing years ago with the objective of raising standard and ensuring employment for rural house hold. It aims at enhancing lively hood security by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every rural household especially for women. So that the main beneficiaries of MGNREGA are women. Women socio economic development is a process by which women gain greater control over material and intellectual resources which will assist them to increase their self-reliance and enhance them to assert their independent right and challenge the ideology of patriarchy and the gender-based discrimination against women.

With every status certain privileges, rights and duties are associated. By implementing certain employment programmes it is assumed that it may leads to the development of women both social and economic aspects. So, the researcher tries to know about the efficacy of the MGNREGA in the socio-economic development of women in Aralam Grama Panchayath.

The social status of women means to create an enabling environment through various affirmative development policies and programmes for development of women besides providing them easy and equal access to all the basic minimum services as to enable them to realize their full potential. Economic status is an economic measure of a person's family's economic position based on income and occupation. So that it is assumed that the women become empowered through the MGNREGA scheme, so that the researcher has interested in investigating the socio-economic development of women as a part of upliftment and so the topic of research is named as "efficacy of MGNREGA in socio economic development of women".

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The Government of India has introduced various employment generation programmes to meet the problems of poverty unemployment from time to time MGNREGA is the first programme in India that has promised to provide the legal right to work. Though the main aim of the Act is to generate employment in rural areas, apart from this there are other certain benefits that lies in the Act in the form of women empowerment. As our society is a highly male dominated the women cannot make decision on their own without consulting their husbands or fathers neither do have control over household productive activity such as farming. But these women usually contribute to farming activities such as harvesting and storage of farm produce which are controlled by the male members of the house. Therefore, it is necessary to know their opinion regarding the programme to get the clear picture about the success of MGNREGA.

Though many studies have been conducted on women empowerment through MGNREGA, Aralam panchayath remained under researched. In this aspect the present study aims to fill this gap. The study will help you to understand about the importance of MGNREGA in empowering the women in the society. The study helps to find whether the upliftment given by the Government is good or not.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The purpose of literature review is "to determine the extent to which the topic under study is covered in the existing body of knowledge". Thus, review of literature helps not only in gaining knowledge about topic but also helps to increase interest in information seeking

and critical appraisal of an issue. As such, an attempt has been made in this chapter to review studies related to women empowerment and MGNREGA.

STUDIES RELATED TO WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Shabbir (2014), “Women’s Empowerment: Concept and Beyond”. This paper tells us about the empowerment of women. Nowadays women empowerment is most focused point and everybody is raising voice for the empowerment but we need to understand first about what is empowerment. Without understanding the real meaning of empowerment, we cannot work on it and also, we cannot justify this movement. This paper tells us about the concept of women empowerment with a real meaning of empowerment. So, we can help in this women empowerment movement with a right step and support women.

G. Xavier (2014), “A Brief Discussion on Empowerment of Women in India”. This paper tells us about the importance of education in India for women empowerment. Indian government has started many girls school, Girls College for the education of women but still women are not getting education in our society. Very few women achieve a high position in the society.

V. Rajalakshmi (2015), “Empowering Through Education with Special Reference to Indian Economy”. No country can develop well without the proper develop of women. The same condition, we see in India that many few women are giving the contribution in the development of the country. Education is the pioneer of the development of women and also of the country.

Deepta, (2019), much use the term empowerment without understanding what it really means. A literature review resulted in no clear definition of the concept, especially one that could cross-disciplinary lines. This article defines empowerment as a multi-dimensional social process that helps people gain control over their own lives. It is a process that fosters power in people for use in their own lives, their communities and in their society, by acting on issues they define as important. The Connecticut People Empowering People program uses this definition to connect research, theory, and practice.

Shivani, (2019) Women empowerment and economic development are closely related: in one direction, development alone can play a major role in driving down inequality between men and women; in the other direction, empowering women may benefit development. Does this imply that pushing just one of these two levers would set a virtuous circle in motion? This paper reviews the literature on both sides of the empowerment—development nexus, and argues that the interrelationships are probably too weak to be self-sustaining, and that continuous policy commitment to equality for its own sake may be needed to bring about equality between men and women.

Deepta (2019), “Impact of Micro Finance on women Empowerment: An Empirical Evidence from Andhra Pradesh”. The study evaluates the effectiveness of the work microfinance on women empowerment. Study is done on the married women who have a single child also. This microfinance helps to evaluate the importance of women empowerment and gives the information about mobility, legal awareness, family decision and economic security.

Shivani (2019), “Women Empowerment Through Self Help Groups in Tamil Nadu, India”. Women have the right to live in the society with freedom and dignity but the reality is fully different. The empowerment of women in rural areas is a big challenge and it’s very difficult to do the work. Self-employment for women to remove their poverty is a big challenge.

STUDIES RELATED TO MGNREGA

N. Shihabuddin (2013), discussed the significance of NREGA. The study pointed out that the significance of NREGA lay in the fact that it operated at different stages. It created a social safety net for the vulnerable sections of the community by providing a guaranteed employment opportunity, when the other employment alternatives were insufficient or inadequate. It added a positive dimension for equality to the process of growth and development. The choice of works suggested in the Act addressed causes of unending poverty like drought, deforestation and soil erosion, so that the process of employment was maintained on a sustainable basis. This was the first time a country had passed a law of this nature and scale, guaranteeing livelihood security to rural households, thereby rural women can be empowered and secure livelihoods.

N. Shihabudeen (2013) in their study reported that there was a change in the policy approaches of the concept welfare from development in the seventies to the eighties and the empowerment concept in the nineties. Globalization has had a negative impact on women's sector and in the real sense women were the victims of violence, harassment, dowry killing, honour killing, gender discrepancy and inequality in all spheres of life. The situation was very poor among marginalized women in the unorganized sector. The study concluded that the women empowerment was a tool for poverty eradication and development making for economic growth.

N. Shihabudeen (2013) assessed the socio-economic characteristics of MGNREGS beneficiaries and the livelihood enhancement of rural communities through the MGNREGS programmes. The backward districts of Wayanad and Palakkad were selected for the study. The study disclosed the positive impact on physical capital, economic capital, human capital, social capital in the rural livelihood. After the implementation of the scheme, natural capital also improved in the sample district. The study concluded that in Kerala, MGNREGS implementation had achieved a very good status as compared to the other states in India.

G. Xavier (2014) determined the scope of women empowerment through MGNREGA in Palakkad. The results of the study showed that MGNREGA had made the women beneficiaries economically independent and it was also concluded that the programme had laid a foundation for self-esteem and independence for women beneficiaries.

G. Xavier (2014) assessing the impact of NREGS on employment generation and wages of the worker households, potential benefits of the assets created under the scheme to the society as well as organizational arrangements for planning and implementation of the scheme. The study has been conducted in Madikkai, Ajanoor and Trikarapur Panchayats of Kasaragod district of Kerala. The study has been conducted in 2009 based on personal interviews and preliminary observations which later concludes that the role of gram Sabha in formulation of a ward level action plan is found to be weak whereas the percentage age of man-days generation for SC and ST categories is very low compared to that of the general category constituted the major beneficiaries of NREGA. The suggestions made by them are that gram panchayat should be strengthened by providing sufficient staff.

R.P Saharia (2014) study focused on women participation in MGNREGA in Kashmir. The study shows that role of women in MGNREGA is a distant dream of achieving for it was meant and finds that Kashmir has the lowest percentage of women participation.

R.P Saharia (2014) in their study also found that MGNREGA holds the powerful prospect of bringing major changes in the lives of women. MGNREGA is playing a substantial role in empowering women economically and laying the basis for greater independence and self-esteem.

G.Xavier (2014) in their study try to evaluate the impact of MGNREGA on socio-economic empowerment of women in Kalakkanmoi panchayat of Sivaganga district, Tamil Nadu. The study finds that the MGNREGA increases income and expenditure of the households compared over the pre MGNREGA period and the scheme significantly enhances the social and economic decision-making power to women in the men dominated rural society. Hence the scheme ensures improved standard of living of the vulnerable poor, more specifically among women.

Saharia (2014) reviews the economic empowerment of women due to MGNREGA from following angles. Employment opportunity, women as wage earner wage parity, control rights of women in earning from MGNREGA, financial inclusion, bargaining power. The author concludes that some "Gender- Neutral Measures" such as increase in participation of women in planning and social audits of MGNREGA, implementation of better worksite facilities, proper payment of wages, planning of works in phases, speedy grievance redressal etc., will encourage women to demand more work under MGNREGA.

V. Rajalakshmi (2017) examined the impact of MGNREGA gender empowerment in Morigaon and Bongaigaon district of Assam. This study showed that almost 70 to 80 percent of sample workers had meaningful income other than unpaid family work during the pre-NREGA. Majority of the worker felt that they are now in better position to fulfil their own requirement without looking at others.

V.Rajalakshmi (2017) in this paper by conducting a survey of rural areas of district Aligarh (Uttar Pradesh) and by the in-depth interview of women beneficiaries it is tried to find out that up to what extent MGNREGA is helpful for women empowerment by raising their standard of living through the provision of 100 days guaranteed employment. The paper also

highlights the factors influencing the participation of women in the scheme and needs for assessment of institutional and governance system related to the implementation of the scheme particularly the ways through which employment opportunities are offered to women.

Shivani (2019), this paper presents some finding related to women NREGA workers from a field survey in 2008 in six north Indian states. Interview were conducted with a random sample of 1060 NREGA workers, 32 per cent of sample workers were women. The past three years, employment works opened under the NREGA in India have had a significant impact on the lives of women and men workers. In the case of women, it is imported to note that relatively minuscule levels of NREGA. Serious problems remain in the nature of implementation across states (such as the lack of availability of crèches for mothers of young children and the continued illegal presence of contractors).

Madhusmita (2019) reported that the unique feature of e-public wage programme in NREGA has become a magnet for women. In the study, women availed themselves of more than half of employment opportunities created under MGNREGA during the first half of the financial year. Women participation was high and effective campaigns contributed more in Kerala, Tamil Nadu and Rajasthan. In Rajasthan the campaigns for social audit, in which women played a vital role, has contributed to enhance awareness and increased participation under MGNREGA. In Kerala, management of worksites and other logistics for implementation was placed in the hands of women Self Help Groups under the poverty eradication mission, Kudumbashree. It was also reported that the 50 per cent of women represented in panchayats compulsorily and played a vital role in implementing the scheme and also prepared village development plan. The panchayat members have a dominant role in supervising the work-site; it would be a win-win situation for the scheme as well as villages.

Deepta (2019) argued that the recent development of NREGA policy in India has become a flagship of rural people for boosting their rural income, which stabilized their agricultural production and reduced rural-urban migration. The study aimed at the impact of employment guarantee schemes and focused that the agrarian economy characterized by lean season involuntary unemployment as a consequence of labour contract. It examined labour and output market responses to a productive rural Employment Guarantee Scheme and determines the optimal compensation to public work employees consistent with the objectives of productive efficiency in agriculture, and welfare maximization of the laborers.

The authors conducted a number of evaluations, made conflicting observations and attained empirical results on the impact of NREGA on agricultural wages, employment and output and the relative productivity of workers in the Employment Guarantee Scheme, which finalized the success of the Scheme.

Shivani (2019) found that the MGNREG scheme was one of the best poverty eradication programmes of the Central Government launched in the year 2006. The scheme aims at the improvement of the rural poor by giving guaranteed wage employment to both men and women and shields gender equality. The scheme created employment opportunities, saving habit among the rural people, raised the standard of living of the rural people, empowerment of rural women, created sustainable development in the rural area, avoided the migration of the rural people to urban area and largely contributed in the economic supplement process by opening bank/post office accounts.

Madhusmitha (2019) in their scholarly article on “Does India's Employment Guarantee Scheme Guarantee Employment?” analyzed National Sample Survey data of 2009-10. The study declares that National Sample Survey data of 2009-10 confirms expectations that poorer states of India have more demand for work under the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme. However, they find considerable unmet demand for work on the scheme in all states, and more so in the poorest ones, where the scheme is needed most. Nonetheless, the scheme is reaching the rural poor and backward classes and is attracting poor women into the workforce.

Deepa, (2019) the article examines the gendered debates during the formulation of the Act and analyses the gendered nature of its implementation. It concludes that a true focus on women's empowerment requires that women's lived experiences are taken into account, especially those relating to their unpaid care responsibilities. MGNREGA's potential for women's empowerment can only be achieved through adequate implementation and monitoring of its gender provisions, which in turn depend on changing the formal and informal institutions that underpin policy processes.

CONCLUSION

The researcher has reviewed extensively the studies related to women empowerment and MGNREGA. It has helped the researcher to formulate the title and to understand more about the topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the socio-demographic profile of the women in Aralam Grama Panchayath
2. To study the efficacy of the scheme on improving economic condition of women in Aralam Grama Panchayath
3. To bring out suitable suggestions for the improvement in the implementation of the scheme.
4. To do case studies.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The Research design used in this study is Mixed method research design. Here we are using mixed method to increase the reliability and applicability of the research. The study describes and tries to arrive at obtaining relevant and precise information concerning the phenomenon under investigation and whenever possible to obtain valid generalization.

The study describes the efficacy of MGNREGA in the socio-economic development of women. The present study is an attempt to understand the profile of MGNREGA Women and to know how is their socio-economic development has taken place in the society.

UNIVERSE

Universe is important for any kind of research. Study area is simply as the geographical area of study. The Researcher selected Aralam Grama Panchayath (Kannur district) for the study. There are 450 MGNREGA Women Personnel working in this Grama Panchayath.

POPULATION

The Investigator has selected the MGNREGA Women working in Aralam Grama Panchayath.

SAMPLING

Since the population is well-known Probability Sampling was selected for the study. The Researcher used simple random sampling by using lottery method. The Researcher took 80 MGNREGA Women from Aralam Grama Panchayath.

TOOLS OF DATA COLLECTION

Socio- Demographic profile

Interview Schedule

Case studies

The Socio-demographic profile consists of 5 questions which access the personal profile of the respondents. Interview schedule is developed by the researcher, which focus on the efficacy of the scheme on improving economic condition of women. Moreover, case studies are conducted to integrate the quantitative data. Through case study we aim to generalize the findings and reach peak to the concept we undertake. Hence the investigator has taken 3 cases apart from the respondents.

METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION:

The researcher contacted the MGNREGA persons on weekend and collected data. More over in order to do case studies, the researcher used interview schedule for collecting data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table - 1
Distribution of respondents by their Age

Age	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
18-28	12	15.0
29-38	22	27.5
39-48	26	32.5
50 above	10	25.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicated the age wise distribution of the respondents. It is learned from the table that 32.5 percent of the respondents belonged to the age group of 39-48. And 27.5 percent of the respondents are from the age group between 29-38. The 25 percent of the respondents is from the age group of 50 and above and only 18- 28 percent of the respondents were from the age group between 18-28.

Eighteen is the minimum age to enter into MGNREGA. It shows that mostly aged person enter into MGNREGA as there is no other employment option for them in rural area. The participation of youth is very low because of their higher educational qualification.

Table -2
Distribution of the respondents by their Marital Status

Marital Status	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Married	74	92.5
Unmarried	4	5.0
Widow	2	2.5

Source: Primary Data

Above table showed that 74 respondents are married. A Huge majority of the respondents (92 percent) are married. Remaining 5 percent of the respondents are widow and 3 percent are unmarried.

It can be interpreted that MGNREGA is taking care of livelihood of widowed and unmarried women too.

Table -3
Distribution of the respondents by their details of children

Details of Children	No. of respondents	
	n=80	
		Percentage
Yes	78	97.5
No	2	2.5

Source: Primary Data

Above table showed that majority (97.5) of the respondents is having children and only 2.5 percent of the respondents are not having children.

Table -4
Distribution of the respondents by their number of children

Number of Children	No. of respondents	
	n=80	
		Percentage
1-2	72	90.0
3-4	6	7.5
5 and above	2	2.5

Source: Primary Data

This table showed that majority of the family is having 1 to 2 children (90 percent). 8 percent of them are having 3-4 children and only 2 percent of families are having more than 5 children.

Table -5
Distribution of the respondents by their children's educational status

Children's Educational Status	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Primary	12	15.0
High School	22	27.5
Higher Secondary	16	20.0
Above Higher Secondary	30	37.5

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed the educational status of their children and the table shows that 15 respondents that are 37.5 percent are having above higher secondary education. 20 percent are having higher secondary education. 27.5 percent are having high school level education and 15 percent are having only primary education.

It is also proved that majority of the children have only went up to higher secondary education it is due to the poverty that they are forced to enter into the work and to find earnings for their livelihood.

Table - 6
Distribution of respondents by their details of education

Details of Education	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Literate	70	87.5
Partially literate	2	2.5
Not literate	10	10.0

Source: Primary Data

The Table 6 showed that majority (87.5 percent) of the respondents is having basic education and only 10 percent of the respondents are not literate. It is proved that most of the respondents were able to achieve basic level of education.

Table -7
Distribution of the respondents by their educational status

Respondent's Educational Status	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Primary	48	60.0
High School	16	20.0
Higher Secondary	10	12.5
Above Higher Secondary	6	7.5

Source: Primary Data

Above table showed that all the respondents are educated and majority (60 percent) of the respondents has primary education. 20 percent of the respondents have high school education. 12.5 percent of the respondents have higher secondary education and 7.5 percent of respondents are having above higher secondary education.

It is proved from the table that only 6 respondents were having an education above higher secondary. Thus, we can say that people with higher education did not choose MGNREGP.

Table - 8
Distribution of respondents by their details Job Status before Joining MGNREGA

Details of Job Status	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	60	75.0
No	20	25.0

Source: Primary Data

The Table 8 showed that 75 percent of the respondents were not having any job before entering MGNREGA. Only 25 percent of the respondents were engaged in job before entering into MGNREGA. It is also proved that MGNREGA have helped them to attain a job and a proper income from that job.

Table -9
Distribution of the respondents by their Job Details before joining MGNREGA

Job details before joining	No. of respondents	Percentage
MGNREGA	n=80	
Sales Staff	20	25.0
Daily Wage	50	62.5
Others	10	12.5

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed the job details of respondents before entering MGNREGA. It showed that most of the respondents (62.5 percent) were working for daily wages. 25 percent of the respondents were sales staff in various shops and 12.5 percent was engaged in other kind of jobs.

Table - 10
Distribution of respondents by their areas of change after entering MGNREGA

Areas of change	No. of respondents	Percentage
	n=80	
Yes	80	100.0
No	0	0

The table 10 showed the change in the respondent's Life after entering MGNREGA. It shows that MGNREGA have brought changes in the life of all respondents. All of them were able to have economic or social improvements through MGNREGA.

Table -11
Distribution of the respondents by their details of other earning member in respondent's family

Details of other earning member in respondent's family	No. of respondents	Percentage
	n=80	
Yes	74	92.5
No	6	7.5

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed that whether there is any other earning member in the family. The most of the respondents (92.5 percent) are having other earning member in the family and only 7.5 percent of the respondent's family is not having any other earning member.

Table - 12
Distribution of respondents by their savings from MGNREGA

Savings from MGNREGA	No. of respondents	
	n=80	
		Percentage
Yes	54	67.5
No	26	32.5

Source: Primary Data

The table 12 showed that notable percent (67.5 percent) of the respondents are able to save money from the work and 32.5 per cent of the respondent are not able to save income from the work.

Going through the data it shows that huge number of respondents started saving habitat through MGNREGA. Through saving, their economic condition has become increased. It helped to improve social and economic status in the family and society.

Table -13
Distribution of the respondents by their amount of savings

Amount of Savings	No. of respondents	
	n=80	
		Percentage
1000-2000	56	70.0
2000-3000	14	17.5
3000 and above	10	12.5

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed the amount of saving of the respondents from MGNREGA.70 percent of the respondents are able to save an amount of money between 1000-2000 rupees.17.5 percent of respondents is able to save 2000-3000 rupees and 12.5 percent of respondents able to save 3000 and above. Going through the table it showed that the MGNREGA have increased their saving capacity.

Table - 14
Distribution of respondents by their support from family for going to MGNREGA

Support from family	No. of respondents	
	n=80	
		Percentage
Highly supportive	56	70.0
Supportive	16	20.0
Not Supportive	8	10.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 14 showed the support provided to the respondents for going to MGNREGA. It shows that majority (70 percent) of the respondents are highly supported by the family members.20 percent of the family members are supportive and 10 percent of the respondents does not have any support from the family.

Table -15
Distribution of the respondents by their improvement in status after entering MGNREGA

Improvement in status after entering MGNREGA	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	52	65.0
No	28	35.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed the improvements in status of the respondent after joining MGNREGA. The majority (65 percent) of the respondents has improved their status in family and society.35 percent of the respondents have not made any improvements. Before joining programme they were unemployed and depended family member. So, entering MGNREGA has helped them to improve social and economic status.

Table - 16
Distribution of respondents by their influence of decision-making capacity after entering MGNREGA

Decision-making capacity	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	58	72.5
No	26	27.5

Source: Primary Data

The table 16 showed the influence of MGNREGA in decision making capacity of respondents. Majority of the respondents (73 percent) decision making capacity have been influenced after entering MGNREGA and 27 percent of the respondents have not made any change. Getting through the figure it shows that the decision-making capacity of the respondents has been increased. As of now, they have an economic support, they are able to make their own decisions.

Table -17
Distribution of the respondents by their Usage of Wage from MGNREGA

Usage of Wage from MGNREGA	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Food	46	57.5
Educational Purpose	14	17.5
Loan	8	10.0
Other	12	15.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed the use of wage by the respondents. 57.5 percent of the respondents use their MGNREGA wage for buying food. 17.5 percent use the wage for educational purpose of their children. 15 percent of respondents use the wage for other purposes and the balance 10 percent of the respondents use the wage for repayment of loan.

Getting through this table shows that most of the women use the wage for meeting livelihood activities.

Table -18
Distribution of the respondents by their satisfaction of educational needs by using the wage

Satisfaction of educational needs by using the wage	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	52	65.0
No	28	35.0

Source: Primary Data

The table showed the satisfaction of respondents in fulfilling educational needs of the children. The 65 percent of the respondents are able to fulfill the educational needs of the children with the wage getting from MGNREGA. Remaining 35 percent of the people were not able to fulfill their educational needs of their children.

Going through the data it is clear that most of the persons are able to meet their educational needs of the children.

Table -19
Distribution of the respondents by their details of insurance protection as part of MGNREGA

Insurance protection as part of MGNREGA	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	38	47.5
No	42	52.5

Source: Primary Data

The table 19 showed the details of insurance protection that respondents get as part of MGNREGA. Majority (52.5 percent) respondents says that they are not getting any insurance protection as part of MGNREGA and the remaining 47.5 percent of people says that they are provided with insurance protection.

Going through the table we can say that most of the people are not aware about the insurance protection provided as part of MGNREGA.

Table - 20
Distribution of respondents by their details of free time during work

Free Time during work	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
1 Hour	56	70.0
2 Hour	24	30.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 20 showed the details of the free time available to respondents during the work. Majority (70 percent) of the respondents has enough free time during the work and 30 percent of the respondents are not getting enough free time during the work.

Table -21
Distribution of the respondents by their expertise gained from bank transaction

Expertise gained from bank transaction	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	56	70.0
No	24	30.0

Source: Primary Data

This table showed that 70 percent of the respondents have gained expertise from the bank transactions. And remaining 30 percent have not gained any expertise from the bank transaction. It indicates that 70 percent respondents opened bank account after joining MGNREGA and a notable percent of the rural women accrue the knowledge to do bank operations independently.

Table -22
Distribution of the respondents by their number of years engaged in MGNREGA

Number of years engaged in work	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
0-1	8	10.0
2-3	10	12.5
4-5	32	40.0
6 and above	30	37.5

Source: Primary Data

The table 22 showed that 40 percent of the respondents have engaged in MGNREGA 4-5 years.37.5 percent of the respondents have engaged in MGNREGA for 6 years and above.12.5 percent of the people have engaged in the work for 2- 3 years and 10 percent of the respondents have engaged in work for 0-1 year.

Through these years' respondents undergo with several meetings, classes, Grama Sabha, and other programmes. And the respondents did their social and economic needs independently.

Table -23
Distribution of the respondents by their accident during the work of MGNREGA

Accident during the work of MGNREGA	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	28	35.0
No	52	65.0

Source: Primary Data

From the above table showed that 65 percent of the respondents doesn't have any accidents and 35 percent of the people had accidents during the work of MGNREGA. It shows that most of the respondents are taking safety measures during the work of MGNREGA.

Table - 24
Distribution of respondents by getting wage at correct time

Getting Wage at correct time	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	64	80.0
No	16	20.0

Source: Primary Data

The above figure showed that majority (80 percent) of the respondents get their wage at correct time and 20 percent of the respondents are not getting their wage at correct time.

The MGNREGA have been working efficiently in recent years and majority of the respondents get their wage at the end of the week.

Table -25
Distribution of the respondents by their getting Government allowances as part of MGNREGA

Government allowances part of MGNREGA	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	30	37.5
No	50	62.5

Source: Primary Data

The table 25 showed the details of the government allowances that respondents get as part of the MGNREGA. The most of the respondents (62.5 percent) says that they are not getting allowances from the government and 37.5 percent of the respondents say that they are getting allowances from the government.

The respondents are not aware about the allowance provided by the government. The workers of MGNREGA are provided with an allowance of 1000 rupees for ONAM if they have finished 100 days of job.

Table - 26
Distribution of respondents by getting Mental Satisfaction from the job

Mental Satisfaction from the job	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Highly satisfied	48	60.0
Satisfied	24	30.0
Less satisfied	8	10.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed that majority (60 percent) of the respondents is mentally satisfied during the work of MGNREGA. 30 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied and only 10 percent of the respondents are not satisfied with the job of MGNREGA.

Table -27
Distribution of the respondents by their safety measures of the job in MGNREGA

Safety measures of the job in MGNREGA	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	24	30.0
No	56	70.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 27 showed that 70 percent of the respondents do not take any safety measures during the work and only 30 percent of the respondents take safety measures during the work. The PANCHAYATH should make them aware about the importance of using safety measures during the work and encourage them to take these safety measures.

Table - 28
Distribution of respondents by working with Men

Respondents working with Men	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	48	60.0
No	32	40.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed that men work with the 60 percent of the respondents and 40 percent of the respondents are working without men. Going through the figure shows that most of the men and women are working together and was able to provide equality between the Genders.

Table -29
Distribution of the respondents by their work done by Men in MGNREGA

Work done by Men	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Carrying heavy objects	48	60.0
Doing heavy work	22	27.5
others	10	12.5

Source: Primary Data

The table 29 showed the work done by the men during the work. According to 60 percent of the respondent’s men do the work of carrying heavy objects. 27.5 percent of men do the heavy works and 12.5 percent of the respondents do other works.

Table - 30
Distribution of respondents by whether MGNREGA helpful in Women Empowerment

MGNREGA helpful in Women Empowerment	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	60	75.0
No	20	25.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed the help of MGNREGA in women empowerment. The majority of the respondents (75 percent) have the opinion that MGNREGA help them for empowerment and remaining (25 percent) says that MGNREGA doesn't help in women empowerment.

Going through the data we can say that MGNREGA have played an important role in not only attaining economic empowerment but also play an important role in social empowerment of women.

Table -31
Distribution of the respondents by their wage given to husband

Wage given to Husband	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Yes	62	77.5
No	18	22.5

Source: Primary Data

The table 31 showed that 77.5 percent of the women give their wage to their husbands and 22.5 percent of the women keep the money in their own hands as saving. From the data we can say that wage get from the work is used for the wellbeing of the family and provide a helping hand to the other members of the family.

Table - 32
Distribution of respondents by their Wage Satisfaction in MGNREGA

Wage Satisfaction in MGNREGA	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Highly satisfied	24	30.0
Satisfied	6	7.5
Not satisfied	50	62.5

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed the satisfaction of employees in the wage. 62.5 percent of the respondents are not satisfied with their wages. 30 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied and. 7.5 percent of the respondents are satisfied with the wage from MGNREGA.

Table -33
Distribution of the respondent's Suggestion for Wage Increment

Suggestion for Wage Increment	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
350-400	44	55.0
400-450	10	12.5
450 and above	26	32.5

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed the suggestion of the respondents for the increment of the wage. 55 percent of the respondents say that there should be increment in wage between 350-400. 32.5 percent of the respondents have the opinion that should increase the wage up to 450 and above and 12.5 percent of respondents have suggestion between 400- 450.

From the above data respondents suggest that there should be increase in wage to meet the increasing requirements.

Table -34
Distribution of the respondent's satisfaction for number of days of work in MGNREGA

Satisfaction of number of days of work	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
HIGHLY SATISFIED	10	12.5
SATISFIED	10	12.5
NOT SATISFIED	60	75.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 34 showed the satisfaction of number of days of work of the respondents.75 percent of the respondents are not satisfied with the number of days of work.12.5 percent of the respondents are satisfied and 12.5 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied.

Table -35
Distribution of the respondent's Suggestion for increasing the number of days of work in MGNREGA

Suggestion for increasing the number of days of work	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
100-150	16	20.0
150-200	44	55.0
Above 200	20	25.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table showed that 55 percent of the respondents have the suggestion to increase the days of work between 150-200. 25 percent of the respondents have suggestion that number of days of work should be increased above 200 and 20 percent of the respondents have the suggestion that number of days of work should be between 100-150. The number of days of work should be increased so that respondents can have a stable income.

Table - 36
Distribution of respondents by their Satisfaction of Economical Needs in MGNREGA

Satisfaction of Economical Needs in MGNREGA	No. of respondents n=80	Percentage
Fully	78	97.5
Partially	2	2.5

Source: Primary Data

The table 36 showed that MGNREGA help 97.5 percent of the people to satisfy economical needs. Remaining 2.5 percent of the MGNREGA does not help them to satisfy their economic needs. MGNREGA plays a major role in satisfying economical needs of the respondents.

CASE STUDY

Case 1

Name: A

Age: 35 years

Place: Aralam

Social Background

This is a woman of 35 years of age. She is from a poor family. She only had higher secondary education. She was married to a coolie worker. They were not able to keep any savings from his work. The money was only sufficient for meeting their needs such as food, water and clothing. They are having two children; the children are studying in a village school. They were not able to provide better studying facility to the children. There was no proper studying room or studying table for the children.

Before entering into MGNREGA she was working for daily wages and the wage was not regular. As she entered into MGNREGA she was able to get an income on a regular basis. Through the wage from MGNREGA she was able to provide a helping hand to her husband. She was able to spend the income on the educational purpose of the children. They were not having much electronic equipment such as T.V. and so on. She was able to buy a TV on instalment basis and she was able to pay the instalment from her income. She was also able to create a small area as study room and a study table for the children. The work has also enabled her to build more relationship with the people.

Observation

As she has entered into MGNREGA her living condition has improved. They were able to provide a better education facility to the children. The MGNREGA has helped her to have more economic stability in her life. The MGNREGA helped them to improve their life condition. They were able to set up a studying room for the children and were able to prepare a better studying facility and were able to buy electronic equipment. Now she is able to provide a helping hand to her husband and it is a great aid for her husband.

Case 2

Name: B

Age: 34

place: Veerpad

Social background

This is a 34-year-old woman. She is from a middle-income family. She only had studied up to 10 th standard and she was married at the age of 21 and she was having two children. Her husband was a salesman at jewellery shop he was died in an accident 5 years ago. She was not having any support from the family. She has started to go for work only after the death of her husband. It was a difficult task for her to find any job opportunities and have started to work in the MGNREGA although she was not able to meet all her needs from the wage of MGNREGA.

As part of the MGNREGA, there was a programme providing financial support for goat rearing. By the support of this programme she was able to start goat rearing. The income from both MGNREGA and goat rearing helped her to fulfil her needs and it has brought an economic stability to her life. Now she is able to provide better education for her children. Through the MGNREGA she was able to know more about the banking procedures and have started to use ATM cards for withdrawing money.

Observations

As she is a widow, she has to find an income for looking after the family. MGNREGA have played an important role in her life. The MGNREGA have helped her to have more economic stability and social improvements. She was able to find a better living condition. As she was not having any help from other person it was a great ask for her to look after the family and she has only completed 10 and was not able to find any skilled job. MGNREGA not only helped her to have economic improvement but also helped her in empowering her. She was able to find a support from the persons working with her and it has helped her a lot. She was able to gain knowledge on banking process. Thus, we can say that MGNREGA have played a great role in her life in economic and social development.

Case 3

Name: AB

Age: 36

Place: Ambalakandy

Social background

The woman is 36 years old. She is from a poor family. She is a Muslim woman and married a Christian man. Her marriage was at the age of 24 and her husband is working as a driver. She was having only one child. She has only completed 10 th standard and was not having much job opportunity for doing skilled work.

She started going for MGNREGA work and it has paved an economic support to her in providing a source of income and have helped her to improve her living condition. The earning from MGNREGA has been kept as a saving for the educational purpose of the child. She has opened an account in the bank and has studied how to use ATM.

Observation

As she was not having any economic support from the family, they have to find a reliable source of income and it has led her to go for MGNREGA and it has provided her a reliable source of income. She was from an average family and the income getting from MGNREGA was kept as a savings for the educational purpose of her child. Through MGNREGA she was able to open a bank account and have learned the process of opening a bank account. The MGNREGA have helped her to achieve both economic and empowerment.

FINDINGS

Poverty and lack of education is the main reasons that lead women to enter into MGNREGA. The MGNREGA have helped them to have economic and social empowerment. Through opening an account in the bank, it has helped them to learn more about the banking procedures. And also help them to create a relationship circle among themselves.

From the analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data the researcher has arrived at convergent findings.

DISCUSSION

Out of 80 respondents only 3 percent of the respondents are unmarried. It shows that youth is not interested in MGNREGP and 5 percent of beneficiaries are widows and they choose MGNREGP as livelihood. MGNREGP is taking care of livelihood of widow women too. Only 37.5 percent of the respondent's children were having education above higher secondary. It is due to their poor living condition they were not able to provide more education to their children. Majority of the respondents (88 percent) were able to have basic education. Only 7.5 percent of the respondents were having education above higher secondary. Although they were having primary education, they are not able to continue it and only a small number of women went for higher education. 75 percent of the respondents were not engaged in any kind of job before MGNREGA. It has provided a great job opportunity to women living in rural area. More than half of the respondents were engaged in daily wage activities before entering MGNREGP. The programme has provided them a stable income. All of the respondents were able to make changes through MGNREGP.

All of the respondents joined MGNREGP for their financial security. All respondents said that they were able to ensure financial security. Most of the people (68 percent) of the respondents are able to save money from MGNREGP. The Programme has improved saving habit of the people in Aralam Grama Panchayath. Most of the respondents were able to save an amount of money between 1000-2000. The majority (70 percent) of the respondents were having a strong support from the family. The wage receiving from MGNREGP is better suited for family love. A significant percentage (64) earns their first time wage through MGNREGP. All respondents got acceptance in family and society. These two facts show that role of MGNREGP in shaping respondents social and economic status. After joining MGNREGP 73 percent of the respondents have the power in decision making in their family and society. Before joining MGNREGP they were not having any social and economic status. Data shows that MGNREGP change respondents social and economic status positively. The majority of the respondents used their income from MGNREGP to pay for buying food. And a significant percent of the respondents uses their income to educate their children. It led to change in their social status. Most of the respondents (52.5) say that they are provided with insurance protection. It shows that majority of the persons are not aware about the insurance protection provided as part of MGNREGP.

The respondents were able to have enough free time during the work. More than majority (78 percent) of the respondents was able to gain expertise on bank transaction. They were able to open a bank account through MGNREGP. Most of the respondents (40 percent)

are working as beneficiary MGNREGP for 4-5 years. More than half of the respondents did not have any accidents during the work. Majority of the respondents (80 percent) get their wage at correct time. The efficiency of the MGNREGP and government has been increased in recent years. More than half of the respondents do not take any safety measures during the work. It can cause accidents. MGNREGP have been helpful in women empowerment. It has helped in economic and social empowerment of women. Majority of the respondents (62 percent) was not satisfied with the wage and number of days of work. MGNREGP was also implemented for poverty eradication and by providing wage at correct time helped the beneficiaries to meet their needs. Most of the people have been benefited in social and economic aspect such as opening a bank account, becoming a member of social group, participation in the Grama Sabha, communication capacity increased, leadership quality increased and so on because of being a beneficiary.

SUGGESTIONS

1. The Beneficiaries should be provided with a greater number of days of work. So it can bring more economic stability.
2. Government should include agriculture works too, as part of MGNREGP.
3. A Significant Number of Respondents is depending on MGNREGP and majority of people are from economically backward categories, so the wages should be increased by the Government.
4. In MGNREGP, more priority should be given to the people who belong to Below Poverty Line (BPL).

CONCLUSION

The researcher conducted study on the topic the efficacy of MGNREGA in the socio-economic development of women with special reference to Aralam Grama Panchayath. The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) 2005 is landmark legislation in Indian history of social security legislation after independence. Enacted after a successful struggle for employment guarantee legislation, it is partial victory towards a full-fledged right to employment in any developing country context. MGNREGA act for the first time brings the role of the state as provider of livelihood within the reach of the participants/ beneficiaries themselves. There is no other study on this in Aralam Grama Panchayath.

Through the research the researcher can find out that MGNREGA plays a major role in the development of women in Aralam Grama Panchayath both in social and in economic terms. It reveals that the women are able to manage their economic aspects of the family and able to contribute their own earnings to the family. Also, they become expertise in banking purposes and also able to make proper decisions according to the situation they face. Their daily earnings through the MGNREGA helps them to contribute the money for the educational purpose of their children and also for satisfying their needs. By conducting the research, the researcher was able to identify that most of the people have been benefited in social and economic aspect such as opening bank account, become member of social group, participation in Grama Sabha, communication capacity, leadership quality and so on.

Through the research the researcher studies the efficacy or the effectiveness of the MGNREGA in the socio-economic development of women in Aralam Grama Panchayath. By conducting this research, the researcher could understand that through the participation of MGNREGA socio economic status of the women has changed positively. Their community participation becomes increased and society started to recognize them. Through this process of research, researcher acquired the knowledge of research methodology and reporting of facts founded. And it was an opportunity to study deeply about MGNREGA and its effects in women's socio-economic development.

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